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ABSTRACTS

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AI tools for prediction of Biomass energy: A Path to Circular Economy Sustainability

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Abstract: The energy business is undergoing a huge upheaval, fueled by cutting-edge technologies and increasing energy demands, which are encouraging the investigation of novel routes. Because of the production of greenhouse gases and their contribution to global climate change, fossil fuels continue to be the primary source of energy generation worldwide, and their use poses significant problems. For the use of fossil fuels, the agro-industrial biomass energy is one of the alternatives. The diverse varieties of agro-industrial biomass materials such as agriculture residues, energy grasses, bagasse, wood, straw and forest wastes are available widely and used abundantly all over the world as alternatives to produce energy. For efficient conversion of biomass into heat and power a detailed information of their diverse physical, chemical and thermal properties is essentially required. The heating value determines the energy content available with biomass thus determining the quality of biomass. The calorific value is one of the measure for heating value which is determined experimentally using Bomb calorimeter traditionally. But this method is costly, time consuming, strenuous and requires well define skillset and conditions for sample perpetration for more accurate result. For getting results more accurately and in less time a better and predictive method of biomass heating value is required. Artificial intelligence (AI) is evolving tool which offers new predictive models for better results and optimize energy systems operations. This approach helps in fighting with climate challenge and environmental challenges by reducing the required resources and increasing the result efficiency and accuracy. Various experimental advantages can be extracted for prediction of biomass heating value using various AI based models. Artificial Neural Network, Gaussian process regression, support vector regression is few of the AI tools have been used for determination of biomass heating value previously. The use of AI models in predicting the biomass heating value is time saving, reliable than predictions by empirical models and can be determined in real time compared to the laboratory methods. However, despite of handling huge data efficiently, the accuracy of the AI based model is always challenging.

Keywords: Biomass, Biomass heating value, energy, Artificial Intelligence, Artificial Neural network

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